

SROC III

Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

**November, 2-3rd 2024,
Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula, Vrdnik**

Delineation of organs at risk in radiotherapy

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Organs at risk are healthy anatomical structures located in the immediate vicinity of the target volumes. In the planning of radiotherapy, special attention should be given to radiation-sensitive organs to minimize potential pathological changes and irreversible damage to healthy tissue. Tolerance to the received absorbed dose varies depends on their radiosensitivity and anatomical structure.

Successful implementation of radiotherapy requires a team consisting of radiation oncologists, medical physicists, and radiation technologists.

Accurate delineation of target volumes and organs at risk is a crucial factor in achieving successful outcomes in radiotherapy treatment. After delineating the target volumes, the radiation plan is created, the position of the isocenter on the patient is determined, and radiation therapy is delivered.

Keywords: OAR, Radiologic Technologist, successful outcomes

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